

FELLOWSHIP

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Mao Gate City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Mao Gate: Echoes of Yesterday, Dreams of Tomorrow

In the backdrop of this vision document, I went back home during December of 2024. I have had the pleasure to visit my memory-road. And this was surely a pulsating moment. I guess, I was on a time machine. I'm likening it to the one you see in movies - like the DeLorean time machine. I have thus lived, in these stories of elders and youth, in this car of Nagrika.

Mao Gate, a small hamlet-town in the Senapati district of Manipur, populated mostly by the Mao tribe. The region is hilly, and cold. There is shared cultural-variance amongst the neighbouring tribes, and agriculture is the pre-eminent occupation. There is history of indigenous Naga cosmology, the relics (living included) are found throughout the various villages of the region.

Everyday Life

Between Fields and Futures

I met Athikho Ashuni, a young graduate, her life in Mao area still reverberate of a simpler time. *"My typical day as a child involved waking up, doing household chores, going to school, and then coming back home to fetch water from nearby water sources."* It's also a picture of daily life deeply connected to the land and its resources. Agriculture, as Elder Adaphro, who grew up in the village, remembers from her own childhood, was central. *"During my childhood, I spent most of my time helping in the fields and tending to cows and buffaloes."* The fields, once reached by long walks and now more easily accessible by car (though, as the elder notes, *"no one walks together anymore"*), remains very powerful for the social-landscape of the region.

Even an officer, working in the Manipur Finance Service (MFS), recalls his childhood centered around farming, *"Working in the paddy fields, helping our parents - Agriculture was a part of our culture."* But time, like a river, keeps flowing, and Mao is changing. The MFS officer, reflecting on the decades, notes, *"When we were small, there was hardly any development in the village... Comparing the 1980s and 1990s to the present, we can see significant improvements."* He speaks of electricity reaching homes, roads being built, and the arrival of internet and mobile connectivity. I also noticed the pervasive pre-paid electricity system in all the houses I visited.

Ashuni, too, acknowledges the changes, noting how

"playgrounds and fields... have changed over time due to development. Many of those places no longer exist as they've been replaced by new infrastructure, like better roads."

But everyday life perhaps, is also about adaptation, like how people make-do. H. Athikho, a teacher, describes a typical day filled with not just teaching, but also going through the often-cumbersome bureaucracy of government offices, like the SDO (Sub-divisional Office)² for essential documents like income-certificate verification, Aadhar, etc. *"The process can be long sometimes because of low manpower and limited staff in the office. It also depends on the internet connection, which isn't always reliable."* Here, I recall the MFS officer narrating *"The Government of Manipur has introduced an online system where they can submit their documents digitally."* This is a very big reality check, a reminder that progress is not really even, and that the digital divide is felt acutely in places like the Mao region.

Again, this development, while bringing progress, also carries a sense of loss. The "vibrant spaces" of Ashuni's childhood, the fields where children played, are giving way to new structures.

Even the beloved "Tokhu," the traditional elevated gathering spot, described by Elder Katia as a place "where we gathered to sing folk songs and listen to folk tales," is facing change. Rev. Loli Kape, ex-Principal of Asumi Christian Institute, Mao laments its declining role, *"traditionally, the Tokhu (elevated gathering spot) played a very important role in village life... Unfortunately, the practice is gradually declining... though he acknowledges recent initiatives to revive it."* While there are surely efforts to revive it, something precious, a space for wisdom and community dialogue, seems to be slowly slipping away.

Figure 1
Source: Author

The survival and growth of these businesses have hinged on their ability to adapt to changing markets and trends while maintaining their artisanal heritage.

Figure 2
Source: Author

The next day, I headed up towards the market at Mao Gate, and it was for sure, a small vibrant space, gushing with people. As described by Lophro, a youth, it's a hub of activity, a place "where people gather for shopping," and where the familiar flavors of "Puri, Chow, and Momo" can be found. And I might digress, this chow and momo (my favourite-combo and I am confident this sentiment is voraciously shared amongst all the youths in the region) was particularly very sumptuous at a small shop right in the corner of the market. I spent Rs. 300 over there. But even here, change is evident, with Lophro noting that *"prices have gone up, and some food items are better in quality now."* This simple observation speaks volumes about the economic shifts impacting the town. The taste palettes have changed considerably, as recalled by Elder Adaphro who remembered *"eating Bora and Daborti (loaf/bread)"*, but now remarks happily that, *"there are so many varieties of snacks available in the village"*.

Alongside these shifts, my interaction with Akha A, who is an Administrative Officer with New India Assurance, really reveals, modern necessities like insurance have begun to weave into daily life in the region. Motor insurance, in particular, has become very common, especially for those traveling along the National Highway (being referred to NH-2), as she mentioned that *"insurance is mandatory due to government regulatory requirements"*. Although she adds that *"many also opt for third-party coverage to save costs"*. Though the level of awareness, particularly in the villages remains quite limited, and where people rarely consider it, unless frequent travel exposes them to its need, it surely adds another layer of modernity reshaping everyday experiences.

Figure 3
Source: Author

Voices of Concern

The Mundane and the Pressing

Later in the evening, I wanted to take a breather, I walked across the vicinity of the village, and saw people lining up for water, which, a basic necessity, surfaces very repeatedly as a major concern. I had a feisty climb to reach Elder Apei Katia's home. She is an elder, who has lived her whole life in the village. She speaks of the difficulty of accessing water in the hilly terrain. Elder Adaphro also noted that *"water scarcity is a growing issue now,"* contrasting it with the past.

Alongside the conversation with Apei Katia, it became very exhausting for me after a hard climb, and she slipped in a glass of water for me. Water scarcity became far more revealing now! While moving in that trajectory, she also remarked *"Our village is built on stepped terrain, so there are many stairs. It's tiring to move around, especially for older people like me. Development is slow and challenging because of the landscape"*. She mentions relying on a "small water source near our house" highlighting the struggle for access. This echoes in Adaphro's observation that *"Water scarcity is a growing issue now."* Katia also directs me to *"brine water sources scattered around the village,"* which is considered medicinal. And surely a taste-enhancer, since I later sat down for dinner with her, over chicken curry with brine, and it was pretty good!

These aren't grand, abstract complaints, but practical issues that impact daily life. For Athikho, the teacher, who highlighted navigating government offices and the frustrating reality of *"low manpower and limited staff in the office,"* and the unreliable internet connection - mundane hurdles that add up to significant time and effort!

While Mao Gate has seen improvements in areas like road infrastructure and connectivity (as the MFS Officer points out, *"With 5G, we are well connected to cities and towns"*), although it is disquieting, in its coverage.

Infrastructure, beyond just roads, is another recurring theme. Lophro, points to healthcare, *"Healthcare needs improvement. Compared to cities, access to healthcare in Mao is limited."* She speaks of the sub-district healthcare center offering only basic services, highlighting the need for *"more ambulances and better emergency facilities."*

Ashuni similarly mentions the need for "better drainage systems and improved infrastructure."

Even Ashikho, the elder, focuses on the fundamental need for "proper roads," and I believe points out a very important issue - its impact on transport costs and the price of vegetables which gets inflated.

While RTE coverage in schools has improved, H. Athikho points the need for better school infrastructure, noting that it "lacks consistency." One interesting issue that is common is its young and educated 'migrating out'. Kaisii Arüche identifies *"brain drain as the biggest issue"*, noting that *"most of our best-educated youth prefer to work outside the region due to a lack of employment opportunities."* This concern, echoed by Rev. Loli Kape, voiced the need for skill development besides formal education to create local job opportunities.

Figure 4
Source: Author

Figure 5
Source: Author

H Athikho believes the community needs to be "more united," highlighting instances of "disharmony." Rev. Loli Kape similarly points to "individualism" as a challenge, where many prioritize personal progress over collective community development.

Elder Katia and Pele, an Elder from Kaibi village, and who was the third matriculate from his village (Kaibi), express concern about the decline of traditional practices like sadosii (traditional weaving). They desired to keep this heritage alive. And I think there is a whole generational gap; most youths increasingly do not take up this art form anymore - it's more that they have come to relish fast fashion, which is cheap as well as fashionable but definitely not sustainable.

I believe the first question in addressing all these concerns, is to see it as a collective responsibility, requiring unity and participatory governance. While the MFS Officer, acknowledging the limitations of financial autonomy for District Autonomous Councils in Manipur, emphasizes the need for "government support" and "proper government communication and intervention" to make local governance more effective. Rev. Loli stresses the need for "a common vision - a shared goal for community development" and laments the individualism that can hinder collective progress.

Places of Belonging

Anchors in a Changing Landscape

Further in the evening, I went up to suku-mateh with Esha Ariina, a BSc. Mathematics student. For starters, there were children circling around gleefully. Some places are very special, and for Esha and Ashuni it's suku-mateh, an elevated viewing spot in the village. For many elders, it's the Tokhu, traditional gathering places where elders and young people discussed issues and narrated stories.

For elder Adaphro, the Tokhu (specifically, "Apeh Salew Tokhu") is a place of personal connection, filled with memories of "talking with friends and sharing folk tales." She also mentions the Chitebu Kaji (ancestral pear tree), a symbol of continuity for the Naga tribes who traced the origin from Makhel, with a new sapling representing the offspring of Chitebu. These places are more than just physical locations.

The Zhekhu village ground in Punanamei village, Mao, mentioned by multiple interviewees, is another significant space. It's where Esha played as a child, and nearby, where H. Athikho flew kites with his friends. However, as Adaphro notes, on the ground at Shajouba "*has changed over the years due to road expansion. It's no longer the same as I remember.*" This also shows a common dilemma seen in 'developing spaces', where development often necessitates change, and sometimes, often to the detriment, that change comes at the cost of very cherished places for its inhabitants.

Azufii Christian Institute (ACI), another recurring point of reference, represents a place of belonging tied to education and progress. Both Rev. Loli Kape (former principal, ACI) and Kaisii Ariiche (current principal of Azufii School) speak of its importance in providing local educational opportunities.

In a place like Mao, where government educational institutions have been scarce, private players have stepped up the game, in a unique way, of community-centric institutions, with minimal fees. The question of retaining quality teachers also came up, when Kaisii voiced that "*retaining them (the teachers) is difficult because private institutions cannot offer competitive salaries like government schools.*"

Dreams for Tomorrow

A Shared Vision

Figure 6
Source: Author

Despite the challenges, a shared vision for a better future emerges from the conversations. People envision a Mao Gate where:

Youths like Lophro speak with pride about the "*organic produce*" and "*beautiful flowers grown by the women,*" which is not only another beautiful facet of the region, but have become employment opportunities for women entrepreneurs. While on my way back home, I chanced to see a pink-red-yellow assemblage of fresh flower-laden Bolero pick-up on the way to Imphal, it was surely a sight, although the roads were kind of dusty, and I'm afraid it may not retain the same kind of vibrance, it once had, once it reaches its destination.

I also had the organically-grown potatoes and cabbages, and there was surely a 'sweetness' reminiscent of the very place you were habituated.

The vision emerging is one of sustainable growth. Ashuni dreams of a future where opportunities flourish, particularly in "*skills training and competitive exam preparation centers,*" to empower the younger generation and stem the tide of brain drain that Principal Kaisii laments.

When it comes to healthcare, the longing for improvement cuts deep. Lophro, doesn't mince words: *"We have a sub-district healthcare center, but it's not enough."* She's seen the emergency room in shambles and knows they need more ambulances. It's a cry for a future where a medical crisis doesn't mean a risky trek to a distant hospital. Surely, this isn't just about buildings or equipment - I also recall a certain student leader from Mao who succumbed while on the way to Imphal due to lack of medical facilities in the region, which was followed by an ultimatum to the Chief Minister.⁴ And this is not a solitary case, it is innumerable.

Here, education emerges as a very powerful force across generations. Ashikho, an elder, who grew up tending cows and buffaloes,

while facing personal educational challenges, sees educational advancement as crucial for future opportunities.

Athikho's message for the people of Mao is to *"live in peace and maintain good relations with each other."* While Rev. Loli Kape need for *"a common vision - a shared goal for community development"* have been reassuring.

Esha Ariina, the young student, who dreams of *"a more responsible and community-oriented future for the village's youth."* This sentiment encapsulates the overarching vision of this paper.

Figure 7: Social Map of a neighbourhood
Source: Author

Conclusion

In the end, I think Mao Gate is not a place suspended between past and future - Can I say it a living, breathing cosmovision?

You find a loose soil underfoot towards the Mao Gate market, and the smoke that may curl up from old hearths around Punanamei village vicinity, of brine-spiked curry with 'local' chicken (Emeho) which is shared over cracked plastic plates (usually the green/red coloured) and of 5G signals getting through the phones, sometimes. To walk its path is to tread on layers of time: like the dim-hum of a prepaid electricity meter, the ache in a grandmother's knees as she climbs to a spring that no longer flows?

↳ *Perhaps, maybe this is what it means to belong to a place like Mao - that is to hold the weight of "what was" without letting it bury "what could have be".*

I believe what I carry back from this journey is not nostalgia, but a reckoning. The elders here - Katia with her medicinal brine, Rev. Loli mourning the Tokhu's fading echoes - are not relics. Can I say they are cartographers? mapping a world where wisdom is drawn from the past. The youth here, like Ashuni and Esha, are just big dreamers.

Yes, the water lines lengthen. Roads unravel. The Chitebu Kaji's sapling grows taller, even as its roots cling to stories older than borders. But in Mao region, survival is not passive. Perhaps, maybe this is what it means to belong to a place like Mao - that is to hold the weight of "what was" without letting it bury "what could have be".

CONCLUSION

To also see development in a very different lens, as a language - one still being translated, still contested, still sung in 'Tiger' folk tales and maybe typed into grant proposals far away. The Tokhu may have quieted down, but new spaces hum: market stalls buzzing with organic honey sales, schoolyards where children code-switch between Emela (Mao language) and for a game of tag (because all I saw was children running around).

Finally, I remember sadosii, an old craft, but well and refined.

Someone needs to start weaving now, especially the young ones.

Figure 8
Source: Author

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Salew Kadena

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to make sure
small city voices—often
unheard have the
knowledge and tools to
influence the development
and policies of their
communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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